

Received: 18 August 2021/ Accepted: 26 August 2021/ Published: 31 August 2021

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5373401>

Lipids on graphene nano structures and DNA sensing

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This work was presented at the *International Online Conference on Nano Materials (ICN 2021)* held during 9 – 11, April 2021 at *Mahatma Gandhi University, Kerala, India, 686560*

Introduction: Lipid, an amphiphilic molecules safe guarding cellular content and also assists transport of ions and molecules selectively for further biochemical reactions (1). Because of its biocompatibility and ability to form spherical vesicle structure, they are used as payloads drug and gene delivery applications and recently in biosensing. Critical requirement of using these vesicles is to stabilization and prevention of spherical structure upon their contact with solid surfaces. Although various types of molecular cushions and solids have been tried, graphene with its intrinsic functional groups and high biocompatibility permits to control the biomolecular interaction (2-3). In this, we studied interaction of cationic 1,2-dioleoyltrimethylammoniumpropane (DOTAP) on the native graphene, functional groups controlled graphene oxide and its application towards sensitive label free DNA detection by electrochemical method.

Methods: Graphene oxide is prepared from graphite powder following the using modified Hummer's method. GO is Reduced by chemical (H_2N_4 , ascorbic acid) and electrochemical method in different media (H_2SO_4 , Phosphate buffer and NaOH) to tune the GO surface properties to compare their electrochemical behaviours with the behaviour of pure graphene. The prepared graphene derivatives are characterized by XRD, FTIR, XPS, Raman and TEM techniques. DOTAP (1mM, 2 μ L) lipid in PBS is interacted with graphene modified surface. The graphene or RGO –DOTAP lipid composite is further functionalized using gold nanoparticle (17 nm) for anchoring HS-ssDNA capture probe and applied for target DNA sensing in presence of 1 mM $K_4[Fe(CN)_6]/K_3[Fe(CN)_6]$ redox probe.

Results & Discussions: Cyclic voltammetry characterization of graphene, GO, hydrazine reduced (HrGO), ascorbic acid reduced (ArGO), electrochemically reduced GOs (SrGO obtained using H_2SO_4 , PrGO obtained using PBS buffer, NrGO obtained using NaOH media) modified electrode in presence of 1 mM $K_4[Fe(CN)_6]/K_3[Fe(CN)_6]$ redox probe indicate activity in the order of graphene \geq ArGO \geq HrGO \geq ErGO \geq graphite \geq GO/rGO \geq GO. This trend is correlated to lower amount of functional groups in the reduced GO compared to unreduced GO, absence of any functional groups in graphene and multilayer structure of graphite, indicated by XPS, Raman, FTIR, TEM. Interaction of DOTAP on these graphene derivatives indicate that AuE-DOTAP, GO-DOTAP and rGO-DOTAP results in bilayer formation, whereas both GO/rGO and ErGO promote intact DOTAP vesicle adsorption. Similarly, the SrGO-DOTAP modified AuE shows a smallest change in the CV peak parameters compared to the PrGO-DOTAP and NrGO-DOTAP modified AuEs indicating the presence of dispersed intact DOTAP vesicle on the SrGO. Both ErGO-DOTAP and SrGO-DOTAP surfaces are decorated by AuNP through electrostatic interaction. The HS-ssDNA is attached via Au-thiol reaction to form ErGO-DOTAP-Au-ssDNA and SrGO-DOTAP-Au-ssDNA modified surfaces. These further hybridized using complementary, non-complementary, single and double base mismatched target DNA and electrochemical signal change is monitored. While complementary hybrid decreases the electroactivity of the transducer due to increased negative charge density and repulsion towards $K_4[Fe(CN)_6]/K_3[Fe(CN)_6]$, other hybrids do not alter the same. Both surfaces exhibit high selectivity for complementary and gives a constant linear range 1.0×10^{-17} - 1.0×10^{-8} M.

Conclusions: This is a dummy content. Integrity of lipid on surface supported graphene is examined electrochemically in presence of redox probe. It is confirmed control of surface functional groups on the GO and hydrophobicity plays major role in the formation of bilayer, porous bilayer, and vesicle structure on graphene surface. Low dispersed functional groups with high hydrophilicity are required for intact vesicles. These surfaces are useful for increasing AuNP on the graphene surface and biosensing.

Key words : DOTAP, rGO, electrochemical, DNA sensing

Acknowledgement: The author acknowledges RUSA 2.0 [F.24-51/2014-U, Policy (TN Multi-Gen), Dept of Edn, GoI] and UGC STRIDE (AU: SO (P&D) STRIDE Comp.I projects 2020: 21.12.2020) schemes Alagappa University, India.

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